

Cancer Network Biology

Description

Gene expression data that is publically available through the Gene Expression Omnibus data depository was downloaded. Research was then conducted to normalize gene expression and determine which genes are present in cancer and which are not.

Benefits

Cancer network biology is a relatively new area of scientific study that looks at the changes in molecular 'networks' inside each cancer cell and is being used to chart the life course of individual cells as cancer progresses. This level of detailed analysis is enabling scientists to develop new treatment options that seek to modify individual proteins to halt cancer progression or to modify the entire network of cells and reset the network of cells to a normal state, depending on the stage of the disease.

Determining which proteins are first 'neighbours' of cancerous proteins is important in order to better identify cancer progression. Cancerous cells have also been found to infect other healthy cells in the immediate surrounding tissue by shedding exosomes, which contain proteins, DNA and RNA. These exosomes then combine with healthy cells and cause the replication of cancerous cells, effectively infecting the healthy cell and spreading to new tissues.

The benefits of this research are numerous, but the most promising outcome is the development of personalised cancer treatments that are designed for each specific patient. Targeted cancer treatment designed to treat individual cancer cells and their unique network system could lead to more effective treatment options with fewer side effects.

Supporting links

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>

Accessed 06 June 2016.

<http://www.nature.com/news/cancer-cells-can-infect-normal-neighbours-1.16212>

Accessed 06 June 2016.

<https://www.sciencenews.org/article/systems-biology-tunes-cancer-networks>

Accessed 20 June 2016.

<http://www.nature.com/oncsis/journal/v4/n7/pdf/oncsis201519a.pdf>

Accessed 20 June 2016.